

THE NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE RED EDGE INDEX (NDRE) IN GRAIN YIELD AND BIOMASS ESTIMATION IN MAIZE (*Zea mays* L.)

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Abstract

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is considered one of the most important crops in the world and plays an important role in human food and animal feed. Considering the importance of maize production, as well as significant variability in productivity, biomass and early grain yield evaluation may be significantly important. Crop growth monitoring by remote and proximal sensing based on spectral information could provide promising results in its prediction. In the present study, an active multispectral proximate sensor, namely the Plant-O-Meter (POM) was used in the field trial to provide early yield and biomass estimation in maize crops. The maize crop was grown under field trial conditions with various levels of nitrogen application. This study investigated the contribution of the Normalized Difference Red Edge Index (NDRE) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) on maize grain yield and biomass estimation during the season. The canopy reflectance was measured between the 4-leaf growth stages (V4) and the end of the tasseling and silking stage (VT/R1) in maize. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was applied to determine the correlations between grain yield and biomass with the NDRE and NDVI indices throughout the growing season. Maize grain yield showed a more significant positive relationship with both indices across the V4 stage, while biomass estimation showed the highest correlation at the VT/R1 growth stages. These results imply that NDRE and NDVI indices may be suitable for early yield and biomass estimation, while their accuracy depends on the growth stage of maize.

Key words: *maize, yield, biomass, proximal sensors.*

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most important cereal crops and has the most notable global production, providing human food, animal feed and feedstock for numerous industrial products and biofuel production (Cardador-Martínez et al., 2011). Despite the genetic improvement and high progress in the selection of new maize genotypes, the grain yield potential of maize is still unpredictable and largely affected by abiotic and biotic factors, as well as by a certain combination of different factors (Ljubičić et al., 2023). In maize cultivation, nitrogen (N) management has a significant impact on yield quantity and quality, and it is required for optimal maize development, photosynthesis, and grain production during the growing season. Since the maize crop requires more nitrogen than the soil can supply, it is common practice to apply nitrogen fertilizer. Still, soil nitrogen availability is not persistent, and its amount depends on various elements, such as water status, soil type and meteorological conditions. Therefore, forecasting yield and yield related traits of maize before harvest is becoming increasingly important in areas where climate uncertainty has become prevalent, as well as to recognize environmental stress and mitigate its negative impact on plant growth. Recent studies showed that remote sensing has been applied quite successfully

to monitoring open fields and large areas, which provides rapid data collection over wide field areas (Kostić et al., 2016; Ljubičić et al., 2018). The main characteristic of remote and proximal sensing technology in agriculture is that it presents non-destructive measurements and real-time plant monitoring based on canopy reflectance measurements. Depending on the surface's optical characteristics, light is absorbed, transmitted, or reflected. Plants reflect light emitted during different physiological processes or morphological components, while different sensors can detect the fraction of light that a surface reflects. Advancements in canopy reflectance detection accuracy have led to linking specific wavelengths with specific plant traits, physiological processes, or morphological parameters, as well as yield and biomass estimation (Sarlikioti, 2011). Several studies have been conducted to identify the combinations of reflectance at various wavelengths to properly account of the effect of impacting elements on the relationship between plant reflectance and plant traits. The combinations of the reflectance at different wavelength bands have become known as vegetation indices (VIs). Vegetation indices, defined as mathematical combinations of spectral bands, commonly assess land surfaces in the visible and near-infrared ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum (Lambin, 2001). Vegetation indices represent quantitative measures used to estimate vegetation activity, the fraction of photosynthetically active radiation absorbed by the vegetation canopy, plant health, growth dynamics, vegetation cover or plant vigor (Wang et al., 2005; Xue and Su, 2017). Over the past years, scientists have developed a number of VIs for qualitatively and quantitatively evaluating vegetative covers using spectral measurements. Among numerous indices, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), developed by Rouse et al. (1974), is the oldest and most well-known vegetation index used as an indicator of vegetation greenness (Ihuoma and Madramootoo, 2017; Zhao et al., 2015). However, NDVI has certain disadvantages and can be sensitive to certain atmospheric effects and has the tendency to saturate over dense vegetation (Agapiou et al., 2011; Gu et al., 2013). By substituting NDVI's red band with NDRE's (The normalized difference red edge index) red edge band it is possible to mitigate the issue of saturation. It has been confirmed that NDRE's red edge band provides better insight into plants in their later stages and is less prone to saturation in the presence of dense vegetation. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to evaluate the potential of using NDVI and NDRE indices to get accurate results in grain yield of maize and biomass estimation. The second objective was to determine the specific growth stage where the correlation between yield, biomass and NDRE and NDVI indices acquired by a multispectral sensor is highest and therefore most suitable for sensing.

Material and Methods

The present research was conducted in a field trial at Ravno Selo, near Novi Sad, Serbia, on the Chernozem type of soil, throughout the 2021 growing season. In order to examine the variation of maize grain yield traits, maize hybrids (*Zea mays* L.) of different maturity were chosen under different nitrogen applications as pre-plant applications. The field experiment was conducted according to randomized block design with three replications. An active, multispectral optical sensor, namely Plant-O-Meter (POM), recently developed at the Biosense Institute in Serbia, was used to measure plants during vegetation. The Plant-O-Meter device possesses a multispectral source, which integrates six light sources into one optical module. Based on six band combinations (Blue: 455 nm, Green: 528 nm, Red: 657 nm, Red Edge: 740 nm, NIR1: 810 nm and NIR2: 940 nm) it provides reflectance for each band separately, allowing the calculation of more than 30 different VIs. As the sensor provides its own light source, it was designed to block the influence of sunlight in any environment. Sensor readings were recorded throughout the growing season, from V4 (four completely developed leaves) growth stage to VT/R1 (tasselling and silking) growth stage of maize

development. The collection of data with the POM was carried out manually by passing over the canopy 0.5 m above and screening the two centre rows in continuous mode at a frequency of 1 Hz. After processing the data with GIS software, the central part of each measured row, or two middle rows per plot, was selected. Based on the six-band combination obtained by multispectral measurements the vegetation indices NDVI and NDRE were calculated.

The normalized difference red edge index (NDRE) was calculated as follows:

$NDRE = (NIR - RED\ EDGE) / (NIR + RED\ EDGE)$, where NIR present near-infra red band (810 nm) and RED EDGE present red edge spectral band (740 nm).

The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) was calculated as follows:

$NDVI = (NIR - RED) / (NIR + RED)$, where NIR present near-infra red band (810 nm) and RED present red spectral band (657 nm).

Pearson correlation coefficients were used to determine the relationship between NDRE and NDVI indices, grain yield and biomass of maize. All statistical analyses were carried out with the STATISTICA software version 13 (Stat Soft Inc., Tulsa, OK, USA).

Results and Discussion

In this research, the relationship between two vegetation indices, biomass and overall grain yield of maize has been estimated. Average grain yields, biomass and vegetation indices of the examined maize crop are presented in Table 1. In respect of the mean values of NDRE and NDVI values, it was observed that both indices showed the greatest values at the V4 (four developed leaves) leaf stage of maize. The obtained data indicated that a significantly better condition of the plants was observed at the beginning of the growing season, which is confirmed by the data from the NDVI and NDRE vegetation indices. The lowest mean values were observed in the V8/V9 growth stage for the NDRE with a mean value of 0,088, while the NDVI showed the lowest value at the VT/R1 stage of maize, with a mean value of 0,615 (Table 1).

Table 1. The mean values of biomass, grain yield, NDRE and NDVI throughout the growing season

		Growth stage of maize			
GY ^a	AB ^b	V4	V7	V8/V9	VT/R1
NDRE ^c					
7,460	75,302	0,166	0,164	0,088	0,116
		Growth stage of maize			
		V4	V7	V8/V9	VT/R1
NDVI ^d					
		0,765	0,652	0,738	0,615

^aGY: Mean grain yield (t ha⁻¹), ^bAB: Mean biomass (t ha⁻¹), ^cNDRE: The normalized difference red edge index, ^dNDVI: The normalized difference vegetation index

The maximum values of NDVI observed during the V4 and V8 stages were expected when photosynthesis was at its highest point and the leaf area was the largest. The NDVI and NDRE of maize crop decreased with the growth process, and through the later growth stages, both NDVI and NDRE values gradually declined, reaching the minimum values at VT/VR1. The obtained results indicated that through the growing season and towards the end of the season, reflectance of visible wavelengths increased, while reflectance of NIR decreased because of senescence and less absorption of visible light in the maize leaves. These results are in accordance with previous findings reported by Reynolds et al. (2012) and Zhao et al.

(2023). In respect to the association between NDRE, NDVI indices and grain yield and biomass of maize the calculated ratios showed that different correlations were found between NDRE, NDVI, grain yield and biomass of maize estimation. Regarding the association between grain yield of maize and NDRE, the result revealed that a highly significant and positive association was observed at the V4 ($r=0,348^{**}$) and VT/R1 ($r=0,318^{**}$) growth stages. In respect to the NDVI, highly significant and positive association was observed at V4 ($r=0,362^{**}$) and VT/VR ($r=0,321^{**}$) growth stages of maize. The significant and positive association between NDVI and maize biomass was also observed at V7 ($r=0,209^*$), Table 2.

Table 2. Relationship between NDRE and NDVI indices with grain yield of maize throughout the growing season

GY ^a	Growth stage of maize			
	V4	V7	V8/V9	VT/R1
	NDRE ^b			
8,460	0,348 ^{**}	-0,008	0,031	0,318 ^{**}
	Growth stage of maize			
	V4	V7	V8/V9	VT/R1
	NDVI ^c			
	0,362 ^{**}	0,209 ^{**}	0,177	0,321 ^{**}

^aGY: Grain yield t ha⁻¹, ^bNDRE: The normalized difference red edge index, ^cNDVI: The normalized difference vegetation index, ^{**}Correlation significant at the 0,01 level, ^{*}Correlation significant at the 0,05 level.

In respect to the association between NDRE, NDVI indices and the biomass of maize, the calculated ratios showed similar correlations. Regarding the association between the biomass of maize and NDRE, the result revealed that a highly significant and positive association was observed at the VT/R1 ($r=0,309^{**}$) and V4 ($r=0,288^{**}$) growth stages. In respect to the NDVI a highly significant and positive association was observed at VT/VR ($r=0,362^{**}$) and V4 growth stage ($r=0,334^{**}$). The significant and positive association was also observed at the V8/V9 (eight to nine developed leaves) growth stage ($r=0,209^*$), Table 3. The obtained results are expected since, during the tasselling and silking stages of maize development, the plants showed the least uniformity. This is a consequence of the different appearance of plants in the reproductive stage, when they express higher variability in leaf color, varying from dark green to pale brown. Similar findings were observed by Vian et al. (2018), while different results and a significant positive correlation between vegetation indices and maize yield in the filling stage were shown by Zhao et al. (2023).

Table 3. Relationship between NDRE and NDVI indices with grain yield of maize throughout the growing season

AB ^a	Growth stage of maize			
	V4	V7	V8/V9	VT/R1
	NDRE ^b			
75,302	0,288 ^{**}	0,016	0,052	0,309 ^{**}
	Growth stage of maize			
	V4	V7	V8/V9	VT/R1
	NDVI ^c			
	0,334 ^{**}	0,177	0,209 [*]	0,362 ^{**}

^aAB: Aboveground biomass (t ha⁻¹), ^bNDRE: The normalized difference red edge index, ^cNDVI: The normalized difference vegetation index, ^{**}Correlation significant at the 0,01 level, ^{*}Correlation significant at the 0,05 level.

Although methods of correction of the NDVI index using the NDRE index should provide more accurate data and a better understanding of the obtained data (Hassan et al., 2019; Voitik et al., 2023), the present results indicated the need to consider more parameters for a better assessment of maize plant states and forecasting their grain yield and biomass. Since several investigations were conducted on wheat plants, there is a need for further investigation and clarification for other crops.

Conclusion

Based on the present findings, it can be concluded that the grain yield and biomass of maize may be estimated with high accuracy using both the NDVI and NDRE indices. The estimation of maize grain yield presents a higher level of accuracy at the appearance stage of the V4 growth stage, while the best estimation for biomass was observed at the V6 growth stage of maize. Despite certain advantages of the NDRE index, the NDVI showed higher accuracy than the NDRE in the estimation of maize biomass and grain yield. In light of the present findings, additional research on various cultivars and fertilisation management techniques has to be done in the future, which will provide more information and clarification for other crops.

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